

Interview guide: Identifying Critical Dependencies in Continuous Software Engineering

Topic	Sub-topic	Question
		[Omit questions if they were answered by the previous response. If the response is known from before (e.g. background of the informant) give a short summary of what is known for validation.
	Follow-up questions for each example of bottlenecks (if participants bring such up)	<p>What are the consequences of [this dependency]?</p> <p>How do you cope with [this dependency]?</p> <p>How has the situation with [this dependency] changed during the latest period?</p> <p>When was the last time this happened...</p>
Intro		Thank you for the interview, the purpose of the research and the ethical concerns. The purpose of the research is to understand how continuous se works in practice and what it requires in terms of coordination.
Context	Background	<p>What product do you work with?</p> <p>What is your expertise? (front end/back end, seniority)</p>
	Tasks	<p>What is your typical work week?</p> <p>What task(s) are you working on right now?</p> <p align="right">What is the purpose of this task?</p>
	Infrastructure	<p>Can you briefly walk me through the different steps in the pipeline that you go through to produce the working software?</p> <p align="right">How long is the delay between the internal readiness and the availability of the features to customers?</p> <p align="right">What are the steps between these two?</p> <p align="right">Which steps are the most familiar to you?</p>

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		How do you divide your time between different steps?
		How long does it take to go through the pipeline?
		At which of these steps do you spend the most time?
		How do you organize testing?
		Do you have any standards that guide how you should work with CSE?
		[Questions about dependencies are with respect to the specific task(s)]
Dependencies	General dependencies	What should be in place for you to succeed with this task? (e.g., artifacts, information, people. etc.)
		What hinders you from completing this task?
		What do you wait/negotiate for?
		Where in your team do you experience the most delays?
		What are the main obstacles to your progress?
Knowledge dependencies	Requirement dependencies	How do you know what you what you should work on?
		How do you know when your task is complete?
		How do you know what the overall product must do?
		How do you know how all parts of the system work together?
	Expertise dependencies	What expertise, apart from your own, do you need, to succeed?
		How do you access such expertise?
		What documents do you need to succeed?

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		How do you know the skills and capabilities of other people in your team/around the team?
	Historial dependencies	How do you know about previous decisions that impacted your task/your area of responsibility? How do you know which related tasks were completed in the past?
	Task allocation dependency	How is this task assigned to you? Whom do you work with to complete this task? How do you delegate/share out the work? How do you know when to start working on this task? How do you know when you should complete your task? How do others know that the task is complete?
Process dependencies	Activity dependencies	Who relies on the product of this task?/Who waits for this task to be completed? Whom do you wait for to start completing this task? Who/what do you wait for while performing the task?
	Business process dependen	How do business processes influence the way you work with your task? Do business processes have any influence on in which order you perform your tasks?
Resource dependencies	Entity dependencies	What do you need to succeed with your task? (people, things, technology, something else?) What happens if you don't have access to this entity?

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	Technical dependencies	When changes are made how does this impact other code modules, documentation, testing? How do you know what others are doing within the code at each moment? How do you integrate the product of this task with other people's work/code?
Ending		What else would you like to bring up about the topic of dependencies? (insights, lessons learned, challenges, solutions, something else?) Do you have any questions to me? Which of the topics that we discussed do you think is the most important? Whom else should we talk to to understand more about how to solve this?